

Richardson Number Variation On Mixed Convecton Heat Transfer In A Square Enclosure With Heated Fin: Numerical Modeling

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Abstract: This study explores the dynamics of mixed convection heat transfer in a lid-driven wavy cavity, enhanced with a vertical fin and subjected to an external magnetic field. It meticulously examines how the introduction of a fin and variations in Richardson and Hartmann numbers influence the fluid flow and heat transfer characteristics within the cavity. By employing a numerical approach, the research highlights the significant impact of fin placement and magnetic field intensity on enhancing or impeding the convective heat transfer process. The findings contribute valuable insights into optimizing heat transfer in various applications, including energy systems and cooling technologies, by manipulating the fin's position and the strength of the magnetic field. Through a comprehensive analysis involving computational methods, numerical modeling, and a detailed parametric study, this work aims to offer a deeper understanding of the complex interplay between magnetic fields, fluid flow, and heat transfer, providing a foundation for future innovations in thermal management and control strategies.

Keywords: Heat transfer, Lid-driven cavity, Wavy cavity, Vertical fin, Magnetic field, Richardson number, Fluid dynamics

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Introduction

Mixed convection involves both forced and free convection for heat transfer, influenced by flow conditions, temperature, geometry, and orientation. Human understanding of heat transfer began with early uses of fire and solar energy, evolving significantly with technological advancements like the steam engine. Modern developments in computing and numerical methods have further enhanced heat transfer analysis and design. Heat transfer, integral to applied thermodynamics, involves conduction, convection (both natural and forced), and radiation, each with unique mechanisms and dependencies. The study of fluids, their viscosity, flow characteristics, and the impact of forces like

buoyancy and viscosity are crucial in understanding heat transfer. Dimensionless parameters such as Grashof, Prandtl, Rayleigh, Nusselt, and Reynolds numbers help quantify these phenomena, aiding in the analysis of complex flows and heat transfer scenarios, including those in cavities with mixed convection.

Mixed convection heat transfer is crucial due to its broad applications, including MHD power generators, automotive radiators, computer cooling systems, and medical treatments like tumor-targeting fields. This study focuses on exploring mixed convection in a lid-driven wavy cavity with a vertical fin under magnetic influence, an area not yet thoroughly investigated. The research aims to numerically analyze the impact of the fin's presence and variations in Richardson and Hartmann numbers on heat transfer and flow patterns. Expected outcomes include significant influences of fin positioning and magnetic field strength on flow structure and heat transfer rates, with potential applications in energy systems, cooling technologies, and fluid control mechanisms. The thesis is structured into five chapters covering introduction, computational methods, numerical modeling of Richardson number effects, a detailed parametric study, and conclusions with recommendations for future research.

Literature review

Research on convection heat transfer in lid-driven cavities is pivotal due to its relevance in applications such as solar collectors, microelectronics, and float glass production. Studies have predominantly focused on the geometry of the cavity, notably lid-driven square cavities, and have incorporated factors like wavy walls and porous media to examine their impact on heat transfer dynamics. Investigations by Mahmud et al. highlighted enhanced heat transfer at lower aspect ratios within wavy-walled enclosures, underscoring the influence of wall undulations and cavity orientation on heat transfer rates. Further research, including that by Al-Amiri et al., delved into the effects of sinusoidal wavy surfaces on mixed convection, revealing that variables such as the Richardson number and the amplitude of wall undulations critically affect flow structures and heat transfer characteristics.

The role of magnetic fields in convective heat transfer, particularly in electrically conducting fluids, has also been a significant area of inquiry, demonstrating the capability of magnetic fields to manipulate heat transfer and fluid flow in engineering applications like molten metal purification and MHD power generation. Studies by Rahman et al. and Saha et al. have shown that magnetic fields, quantified by the Hartmann number, can either enhance or impede heat transfer rates depending on the presence of internal heat generation or absorption.

Additionally, the integration of fins and partitions within cavities has been explored for their potential to modulate heat transfer. Research by Frederick and others on natural convection in cavities equipped with fins or partitions has indicated that thermal conductivity ratios, fin positioning, and cavity configurations are determinant factors in enhancing or diminishing heat transfer efficiency. This body of literature underscores the multifaceted nature of heat transfer phenomena in lid-driven cavities and highlights the significance of geometric configurations, magnetic fields, and nanofluid properties in optimizing heat transfer processes.

Computational Technique

Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) has become a vital tool in both scientific research and industrial applications due to its ability to simulate complex fluid flow configurations where experimental techniques are costly or infeasible. With advancements in computing power, numerical simulations offer a cost-effective means for detailed flow analysis, complementing traditional experimental and theoretical methods. The core of CFD involves discretizing the governing fluid dynamics and heat transfer equations into algebraic forms that can be solved on computers, providing insights at discrete spatial and temporal points.

The primary computational technique employed is the Finite Element Method (FEM), renowned for its precision and adaptability to complex geometries. FEM divides the domain into smaller, manageable elements, solving for each independently before assembling into a global system. This method excels in handling intricate geometrical configurations and is supported by various commercial software packages, making it suitable for a wide range of engineering challenges.

The process of CFD analysis involves several key steps: defining the mathematical model, discretizing the model into a numerical grid, selecting appropriate finite approximations, and employing a solution technique to tackle the resultant system of equations. Each step is critical to ensuring the accuracy and reliability of the simulation, with the choice of discretization method and solution technique being particularly influential in the outcome of the analysis.

In summary, CFD, with its reliance on methods like FEM, offers a powerful, flexible approach to solving fluid dynamics and heat transfer problems, enabling detailed analysis of complex systems that are beyond the reach of traditional experimental and analytical methods.

Mesh Generations: The present numerical technique will discretize the computational domain into unstructured triangles by Delaunay Triangular Method. The Delaunay triangulation is a geometric structure that has enjoyed great popularity in mesh generation since the mesh generation was in its infancy. In two dimensions, the Delaunay triangulation of a vertex set maximizes the minimize angle among all possible triangulations of that vertex set. Figure 2.1 shows the mesh model for the present numerical computation. Mesh generation has been done meticulously.

Figure 1: Mesh generation

Algorithm: The algorithm was originally put forward by the iterative Newton-Raphson algorithm; the discrete forms of continuity, momentum and energy equations are solved to find out the value of the velocity and the temperature. It is essential to guess the initial values of the variables. Then the numerical solution of the variable are obtained while the convergent criterion is fulfilled. The simple algorithm is shown by the flow chart below:

Figure 2: Flow chart of computational procedure.

The system of linear algebraic equations in this study was solved using UMFPACK with MATLAB interface. UMFPACK utilizes the Asymmetric Multi-Frontal method and direct sparse LU factorization to solve sparse linear systems effectively. The process involves pre-ordering columns to reduce fill-in and performing symbolic and numerical analysis, followed by factorization and solution of the linear system.

UMFPACK offers various routines for manipulating sparse matrices, obtaining LU factors, solving linear systems, and computing determinants. It employs strategies for pre-ordering rows and columns, including asymmetric, 2 by -2, and symmetric approaches, to optimize fill-in reduction and numerical accuracy.

One notable feature of UMFPACK is that factorizations are stored as part of the original matrix, allowing for reuse in subsequent operations without the need for multiple factorizations. The sparse matrix representation utilizes compressed formats like CSR or CSC to remove redundancy and enhance computational efficiency.

Method and Methodology

The physical models under consideration numerical simulation of MHD effect on natural convection in a U-shaped enclosure are shown in Figure 2.1. The gravity acts in the negative y direction. The uniform external magnetic field of constant strength B_0 is applied in the x direction. The right, left and bottom walls are maintained at heated temperature T_h . The top middle internal walls are maintained at cold temperature T_c whereas the remaining parts are kept adiabatic. The two-dimensional U-shaped cavity has equal length and height of L . The internal walls of cavity with the length H are maintained at a relatively low temperature T_c .

Figure 3: Schematic view of the enclosure with boundary conditions considered in the present paper.

The physical domain is shown in Fig. 1. The flow is considered steady, laminar, incompressible and two-dimensional. The radiation effect is neglected. The governing differential equations for natural convection flow using conservation of mass, momentum, and energy can be written as:

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial v}{\partial y} = 0 \tag{1}$$

$$u \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} + v \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} = -\frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial p}{\partial x} + \mu \left(\frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial y^2} \right) \tag{2}$$

$$u \frac{\partial v}{\partial x} + v \frac{\partial v}{\partial y} = -\frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial p}{\partial y} + \mu \left(\frac{\partial^2 v}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 v}{\partial y^2} \right) + \rho g \beta (T - T_c) \tag{3}$$

$$u \frac{\partial T}{\partial x} + v \frac{\partial T}{\partial y} = \frac{k}{\rho C_p} \left(\frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial y^2} \right) \tag{4}$$

where u and v are the velocity components along x and y directions respectively, p is the pressure, ρ is the density, μ is the dynamic viscosity, β is the coefficient thermal expansion, T is the temperature, g is the gravitational force and $\alpha = k/\rho C_p$ is the thermal diffusivity.

Boundary conditions:

The boundary conditions for the present problem are specified as follows:

On the left wall: $u = v = 0, T = T_h$

On the right wall: $u = v = 0, T = T_c$

On the bottom wavy wall: $u = v = \frac{\partial T}{\partial x} = 0$

On the top wavy wall: $u = v = \frac{\partial T}{\partial x} = 0$

For the Fin surface: $0 \leq x \leq l; y = h + \frac{b}{2}$ and $y = h - \frac{b}{2}; u = v = 0$

Using the following dimensionless parameters, the governing equations can be converted to the dimensionless forms:

$$X = \frac{x}{W}; Y = \frac{y}{W}; U = \frac{uW}{\alpha}; V = \frac{vW}{\alpha}; P = \frac{pW^2}{\rho\alpha^2}; \theta = \frac{T - T_c}{T_h - T_c}; H = \frac{h}{W}; L = \frac{l}{W} \text{ and } B = \frac{b}{W} \quad (5)$$

where U and V are the velocity components in the X and Y directions respectively, θ is the dimensionless temperature and P is the dimensionless pressure. After substitution of the dimensionless variables into equations (1) - (4), we get the following dimensionless equations:

$$\frac{\partial U}{\partial X} + \frac{\partial V}{\partial Y} = 0 \quad (6)$$

$$U \frac{\partial U}{\partial X} + V \frac{\partial U}{\partial Y} = -\frac{\partial P}{\partial X} + Pr \left(\frac{\partial^2 U}{\partial X^2} + \frac{\partial^2 U}{\partial Y^2} \right) \quad (7)$$

$$U \frac{\partial V}{\partial X} + V \frac{\partial V}{\partial Y} = -\frac{\partial P}{\partial Y} + Pr \left(\frac{\partial^2 V}{\partial X^2} + \frac{\partial^2 V}{\partial Y^2} \right) + RaPr\theta \quad (8)$$

$$U \frac{\partial \theta}{\partial X} + V \frac{\partial \theta}{\partial Y} = \left(\frac{\partial^2 \theta}{\partial X^2} + \frac{\partial^2 \theta}{\partial Y^2} \right) \quad (9)$$

In the above equations, Pr is the Prandtl number and Ra is the Rayleigh number defined by:

$$Pr = \frac{\nu}{\alpha}; \text{ and } Ra = \frac{g\beta(T_h - T_c)W^3}{\alpha\nu} \quad (10)$$

The transformed dimensionless boundary conditions are as follows:

On the left wall: $U = V = 0, \theta = 1$

On the right wall: $U = V = 0, \theta = 0$

On the bottom wavy wall: $U = V = \frac{\partial \theta}{\partial x} = 0$

On the top wavy wall: $U = V = \frac{\partial \theta}{\partial x} = 0$

For the Fin surface: $0 \leq X \leq L; Y = H + \frac{B}{2}$ and $Y = H - \frac{B}{2}; U = V = 0$

The computational procedure was validated against various numerical results available in the literature, four different heat convection problems are chosen. The first case is the numerical results of Oztop et al. [48] for a top heated moving lid bottom cooled square cavity filled with air $Pr = 6.2$. Table 2.4 illustrates a comparison of numerical values between Oztop et al. [48] and present study. As seen from this Table 2.4 there is an increased of numerical value in the present study compared with the Oztop et al. [48]. Fig. 2.3 illustrates a comparison of the isotherms and streamlines with the results reported by Oztop et al. [48] and Present study at $Re = 100$ and $Pr = 6.2$ and a very good agreement is found.

Comparison between streamlines and isotherms for graphical solution are shown in Figure 2.3. It is clear from this figure that there is an excellent agreement among them. Also comparison of Average Nusselt number present result and previous result are shown in Table 2.4. As seen from this table there is an increased of numerical value in the present study compare with previous result.

(a)
(b)

Figure 4: Comparison between isotherms and streamlines for numerical solution of (a) Oztop et al. [48] and (b) present.

Result and Discussion

In this section, Richardson number variation on mixed convection Heat Transfer in a C-shaped enclosure: Numerical modeling is numerically simulated. The effect of Richardson number (Ri) is ranging from 0.1- 10 with Grashof number ($Gr = 10^4$), Reynolds number ($Re = 100$), Prandtl number ($Pr = 0.71$), Hartmann number ($Ha = 50$). The effect of all these active parameters are portrayed in streamlines, isotherms, local Nusselt number, velocity, temperature graphs.

Richardson number represents the relative important of mixed convection. Streamlines for different values of Richardson numbers $Ri = 0.1$ and 1 , while $Gr = 10^4$, $Re = 100$, $Ha = 50$ and $Pr = 0.71$ are shown in Figure. At $Ri = 0.1$ are formed two elliptic-shaped eyes center of the square enclosure having vertical fin. Also increases in $Ri = 1$ flow strength increases near the left and right walls, also two elliptic-shaped eyes increases.

At $Ri = 5$ and $Ri = 10$, the strength of the buoyancy force is more significant and two vortices appear to move down the right half and left half of the enclosure. The physical fact behinds its that the greater effect of the Richardson number increases the buoyancy force to influence the flow field.

$Ri=0.1$

$Ri=1$

Figure 5: Streamlines at different values of Richardson number (Ri) is ranging from 0.1- 10 with Grashof number ($Gr = 10^4$), Reynolds number ($Re = 100$), Prandtl number ($Pr = 0.71$), Hartmann number ($Ha = 50$).

Conduction dominant heat transfer is observed from the isotherms at $Ri = 0.1$ and 1 are shown in figure. It is clear that isotherms lines are more bending left and right side of the enclosure and increasing heat transfer through convection. For higher value of Richardson numbers, the curvature of the isotherms increases with the heat lines are condensed to the left and right walls and the fin surface, which means increasing heat transfer through convection.

$Ri=0.1$

$Ri=1$

Figure 6: Isotherms at different values of Richardson number (Ri) is ranging from 0.1- 10 with Grashof number ($Gr = 10^4$), Reynolds number ($Re = 100$), Prandtl number ($Pr = 0.71$), Hartmann number ($Ha = 50$).

The Variation of the local Nusselt number distribution along the vertical wall for different values of Richardson number with $Gr = 10^4$, $Re = 100$, $Ha = 50$ and $Pr = 0.71$ are shown in Figure. It can be seen from the Figure that the local Nusselt number increases with increasing Richardson number in a major portion of the vertical wall. When $Y = 0.75$ the local Nusselt number is zero and does not change significantly with the increases in the Richardson number.

Figure 7: Variation of local Nusselt number along the horizontal wall of the enclosure with different values Richardson number (Ri) is ranging from 0.1- 10 with Grashof number ($Gr = 10^4$), Reynolds number ($Re = 100$), Prandtl number ($Pr = 0.71$), Hartmann number ($Ha = 50$).

Variation of the velocity profile along the vertical wall for different values of Richardson number with $Gr = 10^4$, $Re = 100$, $Ha = 50$ and $Pr = 0.71$ are shown in Figure. It can be seen from the Figure that the absolute value of maximum and minimum value of velocity increases with increasing the Richardson number. When $Y = 0.1$ maximum velocity are found and for $Y = 0.85$ minimum velocity are found.

Figure 8: Variation of the velocity profile along the vertical wall for different values of Richardson number (Ri) is ranging from 0.1- 10 with Grashofnumber ($Gr = 10^4$), Reynolds number ($Re = 100$), Prandtl number ($Pr = 0.71$), Hartmann number ($Ha = 50$).

The above Figure presents the temperature profiles along the vertical wall for different values of Richardson number with $Gr = 10^4$, $Re = 100$, $Ha = 50$ and $Pr = 0.71$ are shown in Figure. As seen from the Figure, temperature values are increased from the increasing of Richardson number. For lower value of Richardson number temperature values has less significant change but for higher value of Richardson number temperature value has more significant change.

Figure 9: Variation of dimensionless temperature along the horizontal wall of the enclosure with different values of Richardson number (Ri) is ranging from 0.1- 10 with Grashof number ($Gr = 10^4$), Reynolds number ($Re = 100$), Prandtl number ($Pr = 0.71$), Hartmann number ($Ha = 50$).

Conclusion

The effect on the flow structure and heat transfer behaviors for mixed convection heat transfer in a square enclosure having vertical fin has been studied numerically. Finite element method is used to solve the governing equations. Comparisons with the published works are performed and found to be in excellent agreement. Flow strength and heat transfer increases with increasing Richardson number in streamlines and isotherms. As the Richardson number increases the velocity profiles, local Nusselt number and temperature changes. The mixed convection parameter Richardson number has significant effects on the flow and temperature fields.

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